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PEDAGOGICAL UTILITY OF FUNDS OF KNOWLEDGE FOR EDUCATION FOR PLURALISM: A CASE EXPLORING PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS

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Abstract

The need to promote plurality in schools is evident from the frequency of violence, hostility, and conflicts that arise from ethnic, religious, and cultural differences in Pakistan. Therefore, this study aims to explore prospective teachers' perception of the pedagogical value and utility of parental/family 'Funds of Knowledge' in promoting appreciation and understanding of cultural pluralism in the classroom. The objectives of this study are to explore the perceptions of prospective teachers on the concept of Funds of knowledge in the context of education for pluralism and to explore pedagogical strategies for using funds of knowledge to promote cultural diversity. The study used a qualitative methodology based on semi-structured interviews with 7 student-teachers (perspective teachers) from the Department of Education as participants at Sukkur IBA University, Sindh, Pakistan. The population was selected through purposive sampling. This study examines pluralism as a means of embracing smaller cultures within a larger dominant culture. The Funds of Knowledge (FOK) concept is disclosed as a strategy to promote classroom pluralism by embracing cultural activities and encouraging student development and parental involvement. However, teachers encounter barriers to adopting FOKs, such as a lack of autonomy in curriculum selection and authoritarian school and classroom leadership. Schools should foster pluralism through storytelling, group learning, and role-playing to provide an inclusive environment for all children, regardless of their culture, race, religion, or neighborhood. The study concludes by emphasizing the significance of fostering open-mindedness and appreciation for diverse perspectives to create a society that values diversity and distinction. Keywords: Pluralism, Culture, Diversity, Pedagogy, Inclusivity.

Introduction

In terms of their cultures, languages, faiths, and sects, Pakistan's minorities are incredibly diverse despite the country's Muslim majority. Respect for each other is the foundation of a peaceful society, which must be understood by everyone in Pakistan's diverse population. Observations indicate that violence, hatred, and disputes commonly arise in Pakistan due to differences among ethnicities, sects, and cultural groups (Ahmed, 2017). For instance, there have been clashes between muhajir and Sindhis, Sunnis, and Shias, as well as minority communities, who experience daily prejudice in the form of physical attacks, social marginalization, and harassment (Group International, 2022). This is not exclusive to Pakistan; as a result of globalization, cultural, gender, religious, and communal minorities are dwelling and forming across the globe. Therefore, these minorities and various individuals have the right to feel respected and recognized through pluralistic values. According to the Global Center of Education (2019), Pluralism is not innate; it must be acquired via education. Education can help change many of the old misconceptions and absolute values that hold people back from making progress (Education and Social Change: An Interrelationship | Adamas University, 2020). Therefore, to eliminate discrimination, marginalization, violence, and hatred because of cultural dominance in society, we could use it to promote equality, justice, and diversity regardless of the number of different and similar groups of people. In a modern language what we call maintaining a pluralistic society. Pluralism is the idea that a smaller culture is easily accepted by a larger culture, as long as the smaller culture keeps its own identity, religious practices, and morals or values. The smaller culture and/or its members make it clear that they should not try to blend in or become multiculturalists

(Habib, 2017). They want to put more effort into becoming part of the dominant civilization without giving up their own. Because they want to preserve their history and pass it on to future generations. For example, they want to keep ancient rituals alive and pass them on. This study chose the Funds of Knowledge approach to bring pluralism in education through teachers' pedagogy. The approach is based on the idea (Moll et al., 2006). that everyone has important knowledge and skills based on their unique backgrounds and life experiences. In 1992, Luis C. Moll, Norma Gonzalez, and Cathy Amanti wrote an article called "Funds of Knowledge for Teaching: Using a Qualitative Approach to Connect Homes and Classrooms" (Moll et al., 2006). This article first talked about the idea of "funds of knowledge." In their study, the authors looked at the cultural and linguistic resources that Mexican-American families in Tucson, Arizona had and how those resources could be used in the classroom. They found that these families had a lot of knowledge in many areas, like farming, building, and raising children, that could be used to improve schooling. Since then, the FOK has grown in popularity and has been used by teachers and researchers all over the world (Moll et al., 2006). It tells teachers to value and use students' previous knowledge and experiences to help them learn, instead of seeing them as weaknesses. (González et al., 2006) By incorporating students' FOK into the curriculum and teaching, teachers can make learning more relevant and meaningful, increase student involvement, and help students, families, and schools get along better. By showing students a wide range of ideas, thoughts, and cultures, we are naturally helping them become more open-minded in the long run. This will make them more open to new ideas and help them understand a subject better by seeing it from a variety of perspectives. First teachers

themselves should have a pluralistic attitude towards diversity. Teachers too had to change similarly before they could help students change their attitudes and mindsets to respond to diversity and difference more positively, according to [a Case Study on Professional Development in Portugal \(2019\)](#). In addition, initial discrimination from the school should be eliminated, given that the school environment serves as a model for the students. For this reason, our curriculum and teachers must acknowledge that students come from many backgrounds and vary by age, gender, class, ethnicity, and religion. They have various learning styles, educational experiences, cultural capital, and confidence and self-esteem levels. The individual will then have a positive attitude, acceptance, and a greater sense of inclusion. Therefore, this study seeks what are the perceptions of prospective teachers to accept, teach, and embrace diversity and what pedagogical strategies under the concept of FOK to promote cultural pluralism in the classroom.

Problem Statement

The issue is that Pakistan's diverse population lacks tolerance and respect for one another, which fuels conflict and violence based on racial, ethnic, and religious differences. Because of growing globalization, this problem is not specific to Pakistan. A peaceful society must value plurality, and teaching children to value pluralism is crucial. To promote diversity and end discrimination in schools, teachers are essential. Hence, the study intends to investigate how incorporating diversity into education can support pluralism and how perspective teachers can use a variety of pedagogies to promote acceptance and peace under the FOK approach.

Research Objectives

- I. To explore the perceptions of prospective teachers on the concept of Funds of knowledge in the context of education for pluralism

- II. To explore pedagogical strategies for using funds of knowledge to promote cultural diversity.

Research Questions

- I. How do prospective teachers perceive the pedagogical utility of Funds of knowledge to promote pluralism in education?
- II. What pedagogical strategies can be used under the umbrella of FOK to teach cultural diversity?

Significance of Research

This study emphasizes how different teaching approaches can reduce prejudice, violence, and inequality among students from different backgrounds. The community can benefit from it as it highlights the value of pluralism in resolving societal disruptions. Incorporating the often-overlooked fund of knowledge approach into a pluralistic educational curriculum can help teachers and academic institutions foster positive attitudes and inclusivity. Furthermore, the results provide insightful information for advocates of pluralism, acting as a tool to combat different forms of social oppression and encourage inclusion in societies where the majority is dominant.

Literature Review

Diversity is a natural phenomenon in this universe. Which can be perceived from the uniqueness of everything in this world from species and galaxies to psyche and sentiments. Every individual has a different world to think, believe, live, and practice. These differences separate individuals: however, the concept of pluralism appreciates these differences to unite the world under its umbrella. Pluralism is an affirmative reaction to heterogeneity. Pluralism requires people and communities to base their decisions and actions on respect for diversity ([Educating for Pluralism - Global Centre for Pluralism, 2021](#)). Pluralism aims to bring balance between conflicting ideals. Institutional procedures can contribute to confronting competing differences, but

institutions alone cannot generate plurality. They need societal and diverse arrangements of ideas from indigenous cultures ([Global Centre for Pluralism, 2021](#)). Pluralism can be understood in several ways. The most comprehensive description appears to be: A society consisting of people belonging to various ethnic, racial, religious, and social groupings maintain equal involvement in the community of their traditions and unique interests while cooperating toward the interdependence required for a nation's unity ([England, 1992](#)). This means the institutions in the community should involve every group of people in all sectors. So, marginalization, discrimination, and inequality can be eliminated such as in education, economic involvement, democracy, and other segments of society.

Pluralism in Education

Education is an important part of changing people's attitudes and behaviors in the long term, which is needed to advance and keep pluralism in the world. Each society is different in some way, but education for pluralism is more than just learning to tolerate or even enjoy diversity. Pluralism in education is a way to confront the difficulties and opportunities of a world that is changing, diverse, and conflicting ([Global Centre for Pluralism, 2021](#)). In today's globalized world, differences are emerging through various modes of connection and people are afraid to lose their identity, which causes conflicts among the generations and disturbs social cohesion. Here comes the role of education to maintain peace, respect, and balance in the communities and teach people to deal with diversity regardless of bias. According to [Roegholt et al., \(1998\)](#) "The idea of pluralistic education, which is supposed to be a plan for "good education" in the many different kinds of societies we live in, Because of this, the main idea is to teach students to have what is called a "pluralistic attitude". This isn't just about being tolerant. We don't see our

pluralistic society as a place where different groups with their ways of life, worldviews, and opinions live next to each other and should learn to get along ([Colombo, 2013](#)). Therefore, pluralism in education doesn't expect minorities to become like the majority. Instead, they want the majority and minority groups to work together. J. Dewey said, "Intellectual stimulation is unbalanced when there isn't the free and fair interaction that comes from a variety of shared interests." A variety of stimuli means something new, and something new means a challenge to the mind ([1916, p. 98](#)). So, the job of school professionals is both moral and intellectual. Preparing people for diversity should go beyond making them more sensitive to other cultures and aware of their own. Instead, it should make them agents of change inside and outside of school ([Colombo, 2013](#)).

Funds of Knowledge as a pedagogical approach to Promote cultural diversity

The funds of knowledge (FOK) approach was generated in Arizona, in Tucson, at the beginning of the 1980s. Educational academics Cathy Amanti, Deborah Neff, Norma Gonzalez, and Luis Moll created this idea ([Llopart & Esteban-Guitart, 2016](#)). It was generated because many immigrants from Mexico in the US felt ignored at school, so to promote their cultural values and make them feel included, US-Mexican students were entertained by FOK ([Llopart & Esteban-Guitart, 2016](#)). To bridge the divide between the racist policies that failed to recognize the complexity of immigrant populations and the common educational mindset, it was argued that Tucson's student households of Mexican descent did possess a wide range of competencies, knowledge, and skills that they had acquired via their community and place of employment. They believed that by having teachers visit the homes of some of their students to learn about their abilities and knowledge and how to apply them in the

classroom, school performance would improve because these intellectual and educational resources were rarely utilized or taught in classrooms (Llopart & Esteban-Guitart, 2016). In education, FOK can be defined as "historically gathered and culturally developed packets of knowledge and skills that are important for the functioning and well-being of both a culture of household and individuals (Fránquiz et al., 2021). The goal of the Funds of Knowledge (FoK) strategy is to create a bridge between home and school and eliminate inequality of status among student groups in schools. These groups can also include immigrants, native students, students from other culturally underrepresented groups, and students from low-income families (Gilde & Volman, 2021). The Funds can be anything that is being brought by the students from their homes. Such as learning about farming and taking care of animals, Story and construction, trade, money, crafts, art, music, taking care of a home, and so on According to t Gilde & Volman, (2021). FOK is to build trust, between the languages and literacy skills of homes and schools. FOK is an anti-racist practice that has been promoted in many schools for a long time. Furthermore, the goal of studying students' families and community FOK is to help teachers use these important resources to improve language and literacy practices in their classrooms that are more inclusive (Fránquiz et al., 2021). Adding to the definition of FOK four sources help find FOKs, which include family, community, peers, and popular culture, available to pupils. Parents' jobs both within and outside the home and the students' international travel seemed to make up the majority of the family's knowledge base for the students. Peer funds focused on students' support, community funds on ethnic identification and social activism, and popular culture funds on entertainment such as music, print

magazines, news media, television, and movies (Gilde & Volman, 2021).

Integration of funds of knowledge for pluralism in classrooms

FOK is important in the classroom because when teachers stop seeing themselves as the boss and start seeing themselves as co-learners with their students, they can learn more about their students and their families (Maitra, 2017). Therefore, teachers should understand that students' families are diverse in how they live, communicate, and celebrate; their traditions, rituals, skills, arts, and so on. As it is a "transformational approach" that can be used to change biases, assumptions, and preconceptions. It can be used to find and verify different sources of knowledge, to understand and interact with the environment, and to help set higher goals (Llopart & Esteban-Guitart, 2016). There may be a gap between the student's home culture and the school culture of the dominant society. To break this gap between school and home, FOK can be used to gain students' interest in school, especially those from an ethnic minority or a lower socioeconomic background (Gilde & Volman, 2021) resulting in a pluralistic environment by recognizing every identity. Teachers need to be able to teach a variety of students in today's classrooms. To meet these challenges, teachers must not only know a lot about theory but also know a lot about their students' lives outside of school. Culture and language are always influencing each other. Researchers said that the curriculum should be set up so that students learn about the culture of the target language and teachers learn about the students' backgrounds. Teachers should be able to use the cultural and linguistic resources that students bring to the classroom (Maitra, 2017). They usually found that exposure to diversity and inclusion in late childhood and early adolescence education made students more likely to be

friends with people from other ethnic groups if they thought contact norms were fair and inclusive (Schachner, 2017). FOK gives teachers a way to use students' pasts in the classroom. If schools cared about the students' personal lives, they would not feel like they were separate from each other, lessons, or school norms. Also, this acceptance of various backgrounds will help students pursue a positive attitude towards diversity and pluralism in a larger community.

Conceptual Framework

Examining Funds of Knowledge to recognize and incorporate cultural minorities and promote pluralism is the conceptual framework of this study. It seeks to comprehend how this integration can support inclusive classroom practices. The FOK approach has been promoted as a way to encourage diversity in the classroom. This entails supporting cultural activities, fostering student growth, and integrating families into the teaching and learning process.

Methodology

This study is grounded in the qualitative approach. To comprehend people's social realities, qualitative research is a sort of social action that focuses on how people interpret and make sense of their experiences (Mohajan, 2018). First, it adds to the study's interpretive approach to how we know what we know. Since being an interpretive means trying to figure out and explain what the meanings of the data are, qualitative research was a good choice for this study because it is subjective. The qualitative method made it possible to figure out "how" perspective teachers' experiences with learning and learning to teach cultural diversity prepare them for future pluralistic education.

Population and sampling

This study involves 7 student-teachers (perspective teachers) from the Department of Education as participants at Sukkur IBA University, Sindh, Pakistan. The population was selected through purposive sampling. In

this type of sampling the researcher uses their knowledge to choose a sample that will be most useful for this research. It is frequently employed in qualitative studies, where the analyst wants to learn more about a particular phenomenon than make statistical conclusions, or when the population is very limited and specific. For a purposive sample to work well, it must include clear criteria and reasons for being included (McCombes, 2022). The participants were selected according to the following criteria, Student of B.Ed. Hons Semester 7 or 8; Having some experience in teaching in schools; Having familiarity with the concept of pluralism and Funds of knowledge; Voluntarily ready to participate in the study.

Data collection

Semi-structured interviews are used as the main tool for the collection of data for the study. Most of the time, semi-structured interviews used in research are qualitative. The interview questions were formed focusing on the objectives, research questions, and problem of the study.

Data Analysis

The research methodology involved transcribing and reviewing semi-structured interviews multiple times with a focus on the research questions for data analysis. The research design used thematic analysis to detect recurring patterns and themes in the data. The study involved identifying and highlighting key codes from transcriptions. These codes were then systematically collected to develop overarching themes that were most relevant to the research questions. The study facilitated a thorough comprehension of the viewpoints and encounters of pre-service educators enrolled in the B.Ed. honors program at Sukkur IBA University.

Findings

This section provides findings to answer the questions this study aims for. So, the first question of my study is 'How do prospective

teachers perceive the pedagogic utility of the concept of Funds of knowledge in promoting pluralism in education?' this question is answered through two main themes as follows

1. Understanding of FOK of Prospective Teachers

The participants identified a variety of aspects as the Funds from the students' households and their background families' traditional food to their religious rituals. So, the participants do not just include culture but they expressed religious rituals also as Funds that can promote diversity among students. Furthermore, one of the participants identified language as a source of Funds for knowledge as our data states that Jokes in different languages can be used as FOK. Teachers wanted to use funds not just for the aim of promoting diversity but also, they See FOK as the development of skills in students through parents' involvement in schools. They also recognize ancestors' knowledge that might be useful in schools, such as stories they have learned from grandparents. Furthermore, the data connect the literature as the resources of FOK for promoting pluralism. Which will connect culture to culture. Lastly from an ethnographical perspective, we also found the funds' symbol of knowledge and skills that only come from a particular community of students.

2. Accessing FOK

Ways to Bring FOK into the Classroom

Participants suggested various methods for teachers to determine their pupils' knowledge bases. Several teachers use instructional tactics that entail having the students present their interests, write essays on their history, or produce projects that celebrate their heritage. Our data mostly emphasizes approaching parents to bring FOK into classrooms. Secondly, students are identified as means to accessing and recognizing the Funds of Knowledge through

reflecting, sharing, and presenting their practices, routines, and rituals at home.

Challenges in Bringing FOK

Participants recognized the parents to be reached for FOK. They also anticipated challenges in the meeting, contacting and approaching them because of some contextual reasons.

Secondly, participants could predict time contraction, as our schools mainly focus on syllabus completion, and the management has mostly discouraged co-curricular activities. Those teachers also face challenges in terms of resources, logistics, and funding. Teachers say that faculty who are untrained and have a sense of extremism do not like professional teachers to bring inclusivity, and celebrate diversity at schools or in classrooms. Also, they mentioned while selecting FOKs they have to be careful that no students will face comparative judgment or cultural contradiction.

Integration of FOK into the Curriculum

Lastly, teachers feel a lack of teacher autonomy in selecting or modifying curriculum according to classroom population needs. For example, if the classroom is multi-cultural or multi-religious. The teachers are required to teach dominantly based on the dominant culture hence they find little room to integrate FOK into the Curriculum. This section provides findings to answer the second research question of the current study. Which is 2. 1 "What pedagogical strategies do teachers suggest to use FOK to teach cultural diversity?" To answer this question the following 1 main themes and sub-themes have been identified through data.

1. Strategies to use FOK: Teachers identified diversity also as a diverse mode of learning that students prefer according to their strengths and prominent learning styles. Where teachers have mostly referred to the theory of multiple Intelligence, they expect students to share their FOKs in diverse ways

such as through music, songs, playing a drama, or simple discussions. Apart from multiple learning strategies, teachers also showed storytelling as a teaching strategy to provide students opportunities to share their FOK in the classroom and celebrate their rituals, culture, and home at school.

2 Facilitating Learning with Diversity

Teaching approach for learning within diversity: The frequent teaching-learning strategy was noticed as cooperative learning. Teachers believe working in heterogeneous groups or teams helps students experience diversity. Ultimately students develop a sense of co-existence and acceptance of diversity. Moreover, participants think languages play a vital role in promoting diversity and students should be taught in a way in which they are free to use their mother tongue to express their identity in a way.

Teacher's pedagogical conduct of promoting pluralism among students: Participants told some of the ways, attitudes, and practices that will promote pluralism in the classroom beyond their teaching content and syllabus learning. Some of them proposed promoting cultural attires, some think that the use of affirmative language would also promote a sense of equality. To promote minorities participants gave insights and explained why minor cultures tend to camouflage in the dominant culture and feel inferior. So being a pluralistic teacher some actions can be taken to highlight minority families in schools.

Initiating Education for Pluralism: Teachers think pluralistic education should start from the beginning of formal education. They explained the context that in early childhood Education most kids are expected to memorize things instead of developing them the active, peaceful, and moral citizens of society. Where they accept every segment of society.

Discussion

Observations show that ethnic, religious, and cultural differences in Pakistan

are prevalent sources of violence, hostility, and disagreements (Ahmed, 2017). As a result of globalization, cultural, gender, religious, and communal minorities are growing and residing all over the world, not just in Pakistan. Thus, these minorities and varied persons have the right to feel valued and acknowledged utilizing pluralistic principles. In addition to traditional topics, schools around the world must teach pluralism - the ability to view people from various backgrounds as equals (Aga Khan, 2008). Thus, the current study has focused on prospective teachers' pedagogy using the Funds of Knowledge theory to promote pluralism at schools. Diversity exists when there is more than one culture, when people in your environment speak more than one language, and when they represent different regions. Diversity also exists when people have different learning styles, and when they adhere to different religious beliefs, rituals, and practices. The results then present the Funds of Knowledge (FOK) theory as a strategy for promoting plurality in schools. The FOK theory highlights the significance of harnessing the information and skills students bring from their families and communities to enhance their educational experiences. The result emphasizes that FOK can improve cultural representation, lessen the segregation of minority cultures, and foster diversity among students. Among the listed types of FOK are music, farming methods, clothing, food, jokes, and cultural folk. As Glide & Volman have mentioned in their action research, FOK is learning about farming and taking care of animals, Story and construction, trade, money, crafts, art, music, taking care of a home, and so on (2021). In addition, the data links the literature to FOK's resources for encouraging plurality. Similarly, Aga Khan (2008) calls on educators to embrace diversity and pluralism in the classroom. He views intellectual humility and pluralism as crucial to 21st-century

education, arguing that we should expect students at an IB school in Atlanta to be as knowledgeable about Muhammad Ali Jinnah or Jomo Kenyatta as they are about Atlanta's great-son, the Reverend Doctor Martin Luther King. Hence literature of different civilizations will link cultures together and connect every diverse student. The findings also highlight parents as significant sources of FOK and argue that schools should engage with them to identify and build on their children's familial abilities and knowledge. Some inexperienced and radical colleagues may be resistant to teaching tolerance and appreciating diversity in schools and classrooms. This study also agrees with Nilofar Vazir (2003) that the Curriculum in Pakistan is still a "specified fixed course of study" (Webster's) because of this narrow view. Children are thought to be the "beneficiaries" of this official document, even though it may not be based on their needs or interests. This curriculum puts a lot of focus on knowledge transmission, and how textbooks and rules are followed. This kind of "highly authoritative" leadership in schools and classrooms does not pay attention to how children feel. For instance, if the classroom is multicultural or religiously diverse. Teachers are obligated to instruct by the dominant culture. Subsequently, Untrained and extremist colleagues, according to teachers, dislike it when professional educators promote tolerance and celebrate diversity in schools and classrooms. This finding also backs up the idea in the literature that minorities in Pakistan feel they have been treated badly because of their religion and made to feel like second-class citizens (Muhammad, 2021). In addition, it has been stated that when picking FOKs, they must ensure that no students are exposed to comparative judgment or cultural contradiction. Teachers must teach learners to appreciate diversity and difference and to develop positive relationships with others

from diverse backgrounds – specifically ethnic, racial, cultural, linguistic, and gender – for ethnically different students to avoid intergroup conflict and live the highest quality of school life (Baskerville, 2011). So, agreeing with Baskerville the results also showed storytelling as a teaching strategy to allow kids the opportunity to share their FOK in the classroom and celebrate their traditions, culture, and home at school. A crucial component in the results found on diversity and cultural differences is storytelling. People acquire a cultural voice through dialogue and narration, according to Luna (1993). However, because they are instructed to leave their expressiveness behind as they proceed through the school, students are rarely given that role in the classroom. A lot of students who feel excluded or alienated are made to doubt their voices, according to Greene (1995), but they do not have any other opportunities to share their stories or make connections between new information and what they already know in their native tongues (Baskerville, 2011). Furthermore, the finding suggests working in varied groups or teams helps children experience diversity. Pupils develop a sense of co-existence and acceptance of difference. A study by Ferguson (2020) claims that group work is an inclusive pedagogy that offers students lasting interpersonal and psychological skills. Learners participating in groups with shared involvement can help promote successful social inclusion owing to intergroup contact. Also, current results show the same concern that FOK can be brought and shared in groups.

Conclusion

To conclude, the frequency of violence, antagonism, and conflicts in Pakistan resulting from ethnic, religious, and cultural differences demonstrates the necessity to foster plurality in schools. The Funds of Knowledge (FOK) idea can be used

to encourage pluralism in classrooms by embracing cultural activities. FOKs can also be utilized to foster student development and parental involvement in schools. However, instructors confront several obstacles in adopting FOKs in the curriculum, including a lack of autonomy in selecting curricula based on the needs of the classroom population and a highly authoritarian school and classroom leadership. Furthermore, untrained and radical coworkers may not appreciate schools' promotion of diversity and tolerance. Hence, teachers must teach students to value diversity and distinction and cultivate constructive interactions with individuals from varied backgrounds. The art of storytelling, group learning, and role-play are fundamental to the study of cultural differences and diversity. To provide an inclusive environment for all children, regardless of their culture, race, religion, or neighborhood, schools should foster pluralism.

Recommendations:

Research suggests that individuals can better understand ethnic differences and diversity through storytelling, group learning, and role-playing activities. Thus, the study has significant implications for policymakers, curriculum, and teachers to educate about pluralism to prevent ethnic, religious, and cultural conflicts in Pakistan.

Innovation and Research Gap

The study contributes to focuses on empowering humanity to embrace peace and accept human diversity, though it's based on individuals' beliefs, race, culture, or faith. The world is to spread peace and belongs to every other person. Thus, the study opens doors for future researchers to delve into the concept of Funds of knowledge from many educational aspects such as its integration into the educational curriculum, assessment, learning strategies, and teachers' autonomy for achieving pluralistic disposition among students. The study, based on seven

participants from Sukkur IBA, highlights the need for broader research with more participants to increase generalizability.

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